

Leibniz-Junior Research Group

Urban human-nature resonance for sustainability transformation

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)

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First insights on human-food relations through the interaction with urban dwellers in Dresden

Have you ever taken the time to think about the relation you hold with the food you eat every day, with the food nature is providing us human beings, the food which is grown for us by other members of society? To really understand one's relation with food I engaged with urban dwellers in Dresden, Germany who are already in one or the other way deeply connected with food. Through focus groups I aimed to discover and experience their individual relations but also to see how the urban environment can help and sometimes even hinder us to follow the sustainable ways of consumption we are striving for. This interrelation between city dwellers as individuals and the urban environment, institutional structures and the overruling food system is thereby crucial to understand not only current ways of consumption but also to discover transformational paths towards more sustainable and just choices in food consumption. Choices which are not only good for us so that we feel nurtured and happy but also choices which are good for nature and nonhuman animals.

As Hartmut Rosa says in his theory of resonance the "world-relationship (...) goes not least through the mouth" (Rosa, 2019, p. 103). The "world is therefore incessantly and quite literally processed through our bodies. There is no more elementary and no more porous form of the world relationship." (Rosa, 2019, p. 100). Still, consuming food is very often a necessity we have to follow up on during stressful working days. Even though eating and the relation with food is one of the most natural relations we can have with nature and our own body, current western lifestyles do not give us the freedom to indulge in this relation to truly experience our intuition in following a healthy, just, and delicious diet. Expensive organic products, highly produced food, fast food restaurants on every corner, ideals of beauty, absurd amounts of sugar and meat everywhere and every day, those circumstances do not make it easy, natural, or intuitive for an individual to engage in a responsive relationship with food.

Workshop setting provided by the Palais café and Garden in Dresden. (Photo: M. Killinger)

Still, there are already a lot of people who are somehow able to (re)connect with the food they eat. Those individuals were invited to the focus group workshops at the wonderful zero waste [Palais Café and Garden in Dresden](#) supporting my first empirical phase to get an idea of what urban human-food resonance could mean. By distributing flyers at organic supermarkets, in vegan and vegetarian cafés and restaurants but also sending invitations to local projects and associations in Dresden, which root for more sustainably ways of food consumption in the city, I was able to specifically address the desired target group. In those workshops many questions were asked guiding the participants from their inner to their external dimension. Smaller interventions were included as well to bring the participants into

the right mood, to help them focus and creatively think and feel about their individual urban human-food relations.

In that regard, the first phase of the workshop did not only address supposedly superficial motivations for sustainable diets such as the ecological and social impacts of the current food system, but we were able to address our inner dimension. What affects, what touches, shakes, and moves us when we think about our own choice of diet but also when we think about the general way food is produced, transported, and treated in the highly industrialized part of this world? *Mara** did thereby say for instance:

“Sometimes, it is so with certain stores...one is speechless. The masses that are given away there. The masses. And why do we live in such a world? That makes me so angry that in principle everything must always be there. The supermarkets have to be stocked at every time so that people have the feeling they always get everything. That makes me angry. This availability, it leaves me speechless. Really speechless.”

The masses of food waste, the permanent availability of every thinkable food product was discussed in many focus groups. However, the participants did also refer to the horror, animals have to endure to become our food and the impacts those ways of production have on the environment. The discussants referred to the social injustices and unbelievable working conditions in food production, the hunger many human beings are still suffering from and simultaneously the vast amount of ignorance and egoistic behavior of privileged members of society when it comes to their consumption patterns. The engaged focus group members were thereby also able to pin down specific feelings and emotions as well as to focus on transformational experiences, moments, and encounters which paved their way towards a more sustainable relation with food touching already on many aspects around the external dimension. *Eloise* said for example:

“I have read the book Eating Animals. I think that was eight years ago, and when I read it back then, I was kind of shocked. I mean, somehow I was already familiar with photos of factory farming and it never seemed to have affected me that much before, but to read it and to deal with it for weeks was kind of extreme. And then I became a vegetarian.”

Juliane added:

“I think for me what has been a total sticking point when I started to cook for myself, because I find it a difference for me whether the meat is still raw or already cooked. I remember clearly that at some point I think the first time I made a goose or a chicken. And I was incredibly disgusted and couldn't touch it because I feel like there's naked dead in front of me.”

and *Alma* said:

“So I think with me it wasn't a single point, but rather the influence of people in my environment, whether it's my grandmother who grows everything in her garden and boils it down and has a whole cellar full of jam or my mom who always grows tomatoes or a friend who has become a vegetarian and then I became a vegetarian myself. I think with me it's just ...not necessarily dependent, but I've been influenced a lot by people in my environment.”

Those workshops made my heart feel light. Every each and one of them was unique, the people were so open and good with each other. It gave me a lot of hope, motivation, and drive but also an inner satisfaction and calmness with my personal choice of food consumption and with the research I am privileged to do. In that regard, *Philipp* said:

"The moment I start to think about and feel like I'm a part of something. There is actually not much room than to look at...what am I eating? How do I move around? How do I experience myself within this world as a part of it? And that process, which also means personal maturity, is the biggest driver."

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If you have any comments or question on the essay, feel warmly invited to contact the author (m.killinger@ioer.de).

** All participants' names are pseudonymized*

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